

організаційні та індивідуальні. Для підвищення ефективності комунікативної взаємодії закладів освіти та викладачів запропоновано використовувати типологію організаційних культур, засновану на цінностях та їх стабільності. Запропоновано кілька базових моделей комунікативної взаємодії закладів освіти та викладачів, які мають місце у сучасному світі: розширена, звужена, технологічна, закрита, відкрита, гнучка. Зроблено висновок про необхідність гнучкого менеджменту з урахуванням особливостей суб'єктів освітнього поля та тенденцій на різних рівнях соціальної динаміки.

Ключові слова: комунікаційне поле, комунікаційна взаємодія, моделі комунікаційної взаємодії, цінності, організаційна культура закладу освіти.

Mykhaylyova Kateryna. Typical models of communication interaction between educational institutions and teachers in modern conditions.

The article is devoted to the consideration of models of communicative interaction of educational institutions and teachers in modern conditions as well as the factors that influence them. The definition of the communication field of an educational institution is proposed as a set of interactions between all subjects of the educational space, which is regulated by multi-level norms, values and occurs in various forms through general and specific channels. The concepts of «communication field» and «communication space» are distinguished. Factors that influence the communicative interaction of an educational institution and teachers are considered; their grouping is carried out: global, macro factors, regional, organizational and individual. To increase the effectiveness of communicative interaction of educational institutions and teachers, it is proposed to use a typology of organizational cultures based on values and their stability. Several basic models of communicative interaction of educational institutions and teachers that take place in the modern world are proposed: expanded, narrowed, technological, closed, open, flexible. The conclusion is made about the need for flexible management, taking into account the characteristics of subjects in the educational field and trends at different levels of social dynamics.

Keywords: communication field, communication interaction, communication interaction models, values, organizational culture of an educational institution.

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**SUSTAINABLE COMMUNICATION AND RESILIENCE
AS PRIORITIES IN TURBULENT ACADEMIA**

Contemporary crises have a phenomenal impact on the system of life necessitating from the education sector a prioritization of the development of sustainability competence. The UNESCO Global Action Program on Education for Sustainable Development and global citizenship states that:

“By 2030 ensure all learners acquire the knowledge and skills necessary for sustainable development, including through education for sustainable development, sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship education and appreciation of cultural diversity, and the contribution of culture to sustainable development.” [4].

The systematized experience of Austrian and Ukrainian educators and researchers highlighted the value of sustainability competence bringing resilience and empowerment to both organization and individuals (A. Bandura, N. Garnezy, K. Valtl). Sustainability encompasses different aspects, and among them sustainable communication and resilience development have become challenges for the academia to be urgently addressed.

Sustainable communication. Sustainable communication refers to responsible communication practices ensuring long-term viability and minimizing negative impacts through diversity, inclusivity, holistic approach to problem-solving and authentic engagement with individuals for the common good. Critical discourse analysis of the top U.S. university presidents identified [10] the raised concern of the academia strategists about the unwillingness of the people to engage in volunteering and communication. In Yale's

2023 Baccalaureate speech the crucial role of community and service in combatting the growing epidemic of loneliness is highlighted. Graduates are reminded that the relationships they form will transmit lasting significance beyond their academic accomplishments. The address draws attention to the impact of community involvement, referencing Robert Putnam's *Bowling Alone* to illustrate the decline of social engagement in American communities and advocate for active participation as a remedy for isolation. The speech addresses the alarming rise in loneliness, noting that 60% of Americans and a striking 75% of younger people currently struggle with feelings of disconnection. This is suggested to become critical to public health. The importance of graduates' engagement to strengthen their communities and service to the world is underlined by both Harvard and Yale leaders [1; 10].

Currently, there is a strong emphasis on *interdisciplinary communication* where teams from diverse fields collaborate on problems or projects, applying a multidisciplinary approach to address complex scientific challenges and the pressing issues of today's world. Such synergies bridge conceptual, methodological, and practical gaps between disciplines, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding and approach to problem-solving, holistic perspectives and innovations. The principle of 'science without walls', advocated by Albert Einstein, referring to the 'internationalization or 'universality of science', emphasizes the importance of collaboration and working together toward a common goal, seeking the truth, "independent outlook and judgment" and transcending divisions. The idea of unity in diversity, resonating with values found in many religious traditions, highlights the universal nature of the pursuit of knowledge and truth. By avoiding exclusivity and tendencies toward dominance, individuals and organizations can create an environment where open dialogue, mutual respect, and collaboration thrive, leading to innovative solutions and stronger global cooperation [5].

Critical thinking, a balanced perspective, and the inclusion of diverse voices are essential in avoiding 'cognitive vulnerability', preventing disconnection, marginalization and reducing the emotional exaggeration often seen in public content perception [8]. By examining opposing views and striving to bridge polarization, we foster peacemaking rhetoric promoting anti-war communication, which is vital for creating a more harmonious global discourse. This approach contributes to reduce the harmful impact of large-scale military conflicts, which often lead to violence against educational institutions and pose significant risks to the lives of students and academics [11]. Through such efforts, we can protect education as a fundamental human right and work toward minimizing the destructive consequences of war. In response to military conflicts, leaders in higher education underline the importance of 'solidarity and collegiality' as key values for fostering a secure and collaborative environment within academic institutions. By prioritizing these principles, they help ensure that academic communities remain resilient and united in the face of external challenges, promoting a culture of mutual support and cooperation [2]. Thus, sustainable communication built on the pillars of diversity and inclusion promotes *peace* and upholds ethical and pro-human principles prioritizing the dignity and well-being of individuals to contribute to peaceful existence of humanity.

Effective *intercultural communication*, fueled by cultural awareness, understanding of others' values and perspectives, and a commitment to avoid ethnocentrism, 'hatred and fear of one another', plays a pivotal role in fostering sustainable communication [5]. Intercultural competence in online formats is successfully developed through e-tandems that add value to contemporary educational programs. Contained within the recent Ukrainian-Austrian collaborative e-tandem, participants of The Kharkiv University of Humanities "People's Ukrainian academy" and Vienna University of Economics and Business (WU Wirtschaftsuniversität) were able to explore negotiations strategies. The students learnt and practiced communication strategies to reach consensus and compromise within business discussions with international partners [7]. In Swiss-Ukrainian e-learning tandem the students were taught by the Swiss professor about the vital principles of intercultural conflict management and the significance of 'shift in perception of another side's interests' for the overcoming the conflict [13]. In the recent intercultural Japanese-Ukrainian collaboration students developed critical skills, when innovations initiated by the students of Takasaki University were improved by the students of The Kharkiv University of Humanities "People's Ukrainian Academy" based on the marketing survey questions. The improved versions of the products were presented in video. The discussion of the Japanese students' innovations (the glasses to wake you up, mobile garbage

can, dustbox project, frying pan for simultaneous cooking different things, a watch guarding your schedule) underlined the aspiration of younger generation for ergonomic and sustainable life.

Human-AI synergy. Collaborative interaction between humans and artificial intelligence (AI) systems where the strengths of both are combined to achieve efficient outcomes presents an immense challenge today. AI-centered learning and teaching suggests streamlining routine tasks, giving humans more room for creativity, non-standard solutions, and innovations, while enhancing expertise of humans in soft skills such as empathy, mindfulness, communication, and leadership. Additionally, the synergy with AI emancipates learners to develop intellectual curiosity, creativity, critical thinking, integrity and inclusivity that form the core of the academic ethos. University strategists in their appeals to faculty urge continuous professional development and fast adaptation to AI to stay updated with new pedagogical and research techniques [5].

Resilience techniques. Equipping learners with resilience, that is, creating ‘resilient learners’ has become one of the targets of UNESCO [14; 4]. Hence, the prerequisite for strategies that empower students to develop methods that can enable the implementation of the practice of coping mechanisms especially in highly required stressful situations. These situations can range from the Covid 19 pandemic to wars ensuing compelled migration, personal losses and challenges. This urge has resulted in developing and adapting resilience techniques, one of which is to engage and regulate *mindfulness (Achtsamkeit)*, that is, working with the learner’s concentration and attention focus [9]. When mechanisms and factors lead to the positive development of individuals and work well, the phenomenon of resilience occurs. According to Robbins et al [12] resilience is viewed as essential for students to manage academic demand to enable positive progress and additionally to cope with the pressure from study, work and life. Furthermore, Johnson [6] identified factors such as optimism, self-efficacy and psychological well-being as being the most important to the development of resilience in students.

In accordance with Resilience in Education (RE) and Sustainable Development in Education (SDE), the pilot research project for the 9th Austrian UAS Language Instructors’s Conference (initiated by Mag. Krishna Reddy-Hrisenko, since 2016) was conducted within Business communication learning modules at the University of Applied Sciences (FH Technikum-Wien). In this pilot research project 21 groups of students (ranging 11-19) were offered an exercise on concentration. The administered nurturing stimuli (in the form of a guided concentration training and development technique) were tasked to enhance their state of mind and trigger an introspective attitude towards thought processes. The aim of the pilot project is to elicit awareness of thought processes, state of mind and develop strategies to master and muster the ability to rise above the mind by learning the cumulative reduction of thought processes by conscious efforts. The experience begins with informing the students about resilience in education and its benefits and they are encouraged to use ‘multiply perspectives’ approach. The students receive instructions to contemplate on their position, posture and go into silent concentration (a process of inner focused attention eradicating thought processes) for 3-5 minutes. The aim is to increase their learning abilities in the face of stress to calm down and become more focused and aware. The hypothesis suggests that gradually reducing or entirely quieting mental activity can recharge the mind, enabling it to function optimally in all situations, especially under heightened stress. Subsequent documentation of the experience by the students illustrated the benefits of the technique. The analysis of the participants’ observations on concentration sessions showed that 82% of the experiences reported “relaxed, calmer”, “powerful, lower pulse”, “better focus”, “highly effective to manage the day”, “eradication of negative thoughts”, “better control of emotions and renewed energy”. 71% of the experiences reported “light feeling, warm feeling, feel heartbeat, sensations”, “positive emotions/ energy, good feeling, enjoyed the experience”, “free-minded, get rid of thoughts”, “Switched off, take a break from the hectic, “Get rid of stress”, “inner-silence”. Neuroscientifically, during a concentration exercise the brain experience certain actions: frontal lobe (reasoning planning & emotions) goes offline; parietal lobe (processing sensory information and the surrounding world) slows down; thalamus (channeling some signals deeper & stopping others) reduces the flow of incoming signals. Reticular formation (receives stimuli brain alert responds) dials back the arousal signal [3].

This approach aims to foster individuals that can learn and develop methods to apply strategies in current and future stressful situations incorporating critical thinking, introspection and positive reinforcement

on thought processes thereby rendering education as sustainable. Further research should enrich the problem of incorporating sustainable resilience in education as it has a lifelong impact, igniting a flame that touches through difficulties and hurdles, to continually arise to emerge on the positive well-being fostering side.

In summary, academia and education strategists' appeals to sustainable communication and resilience strategies to foster academic rigor and flexibility through inclusive, intercultural, interdisciplinary and AI-assisted collaboration as well as learner's resilience concentration and attention power in crisis can serve as immediate navigation resources to be further researched.

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Молодча Наталя, Редді-Хриценко Крішне. Стала комунікація та резилієнтність як пріоритети в турбулентному освітньому середовищі.

Сучасні кризи підкреслюють необхідність того, щоб освітні системи надавали пріоритет розвитку стійкості, що є ключовим аспектом у забезпеченні учасників освітнього процесу

навичками психологічної витривалості, як це зазначено в меті ЮНЕСКО. Стала комунікація, яка є невід'ємною частиною сталого розвитку людини, зосереджена на відповідальному та інклюзивному діалозі та визнається лідерами академічної спільноти як важливий елемент зміцнення миру та створення стійких соціальних зв'язків для подолання сучасних викликів. Визнано, що міждисциплінарна співпраця та синергія між людиною і штучним інтелектом є вирішальними для розв'язання глобальних проблем, сприяючи розвитку творчості та критичного мислення. Ефективна міжкультурна комунікація, що ґрунтується на культурній обізнаності та інклюзивності, є необхідною для сталого та продуктивного діалогу. Навчальні е-тандеми, що реалізуються в рамках співпраці університетів України, Австрії, Швейцарії та Японії, успішно розвивають у студентів навички ведення переговорів, управління конфліктами та створення інновацій через міжкультурний обмін. Резилієнтність, яка є життєво важливою для ефективного управління академічними та особистими викликами, може бути розвинута за допомогою технік усвідомленості, що показали позитивні результати в австрійському пілотному проєкті, де вправи на концентрацію значно покращили увагу та знизили рівень стресу. Освіта, яка формує стійкість, інтроспекцію та критичне мислення, визнається цінною на всьому життєвому шляху, сприяючи загальному добробуту та здатності ефективно долати труднощі.

Ключові слова: компетентність сталого розвитку, стійкість, резилієнтність, стала комунікація, університет, міждисциплінарна співпраця, е-тандем, синергія людини та ШІ, ЮНЕСКО

Molodcha Natalia, Reddy-Hrisenko Krishne. Sustainable communication and resilience as priorities in turbulent academia.

Contemporary crises underscore the need for education systems to prioritize sustainability competence, as highlighted by UNESCO's goal of equipping learners with skills for sustainable development. Sustainable communication, integral to sustainability competence, focusing on responsible and inclusive dialogue, and the creation of resilient social ties to overcome contemporary challenges, as noted by academic leaders. Interdisciplinary collaboration and human-AI synergies are recognized as essential for addressing global challenges, promoting creativity and critical thinking. Effective intercultural communication, driven by cultural awareness and inclusivity, is stated to be pivotal for sustainable dialogue. Learning e-tandems, as shown in Ukrainian-Austrian, Swiss-Ukrainian, and Japanese-Ukrainian collaborations, are suggested to be useful for the successful development of students' negotiation, conflict management, and innovation skills through intercultural exchanges. Resilience, which is vital for managing academic and personal challenges, has been shown to be effectively supported by mindfulness techniques, as evidenced by positive results in an Austrian pilot project where concentration exercises improved focus and reduced stress. Education that fosters resilience, introspection, and critical thinking is recognized for its lifelong benefits, promoting well-being and the ability to navigate adversity.

Key words: Sustainability competence, Resilience, Sustainable communication, University, Interdisciplinary collaboration, Human-AI synergy, E-Tandem, Mindfulness, UNESCO

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**АКАДЕМІЧНА СВОБОДА ВИКЛАДАЧА ІНОЗЕМНИХ МОВ
ТА ЙОГО «ДІАЛОГ ВІДМІННОСТЕЙ» ІЗ ЗАКЛАДОМ ВИЩОЇ ОСВІТИ**

Поняття академічної свободи з'явилося одночасно із виникненням перших університетів. В Європі це приблизно 11–17 століття, коли навчальні заклади почали перейматися питаннями створення спеціальних структур для поширення фундаментальних знань, проведення наукових досліджень та впровадження професійної підготовки високого рівня. Історичною умовою реалізації гуманістичного характеру освіти стали академічні свободи, які дають усім суб'єктам освітнього процесу можливість вибору елементів навчання і викладання.